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Geographical Information Systems in Public Health: Investigating the Impact of Environmental and Climatic Factors on Encephalitis in Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This study explores the role of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) in mapping disease patterns, specifically focusing on encephalitis in Bihar, India. Encephalitis, a significant public health issue in the region, is heavily influenced by environmental and climatic factors, including monsoons, flooding, and stagnant water. The research investigates the correlation between these factors and the incidence of encephalitis, particularly in vulnerable populations like children. Additionally, it examines how parental behavior, influenced by living standards, income, and culture, must adapt to these geographical conditions to mitigate the disease's impact. By integrating GIS technology, the study aims to enhance understanding of disease diffusion patterns and inform public health strategies, thereby improving preventive measures and resource allocation.

Keywords: Geographical Information System (GIS); Geographical Information Science; Epidemiology; Mapping of Epidemics and Endemics; Encephalitis in Bihar.

1. Introduction:

Geographical Information System (GIS), tools, and technologies are being widely used worldwide to map disease patterns, scope, households, and deaths. Such technologies can be further used to relate the cropping pattern, horticulture, plantations, temperature, rainfall, land, and water management with the occurrence of disease be it either epidemic or endemic. Epidemiologists usually also map the culture of the people especially related to food, drinking, living, dressing, and maintenance of hygiene, and their parental behavior must adjust accordingly to the geographical and climatic conditions. Children in specific types of geographical and climatic conditions require special kinds of care including parental and other social care. If all those do not change accordingly then the menace would continue unabated. Therefore, this particular study would investigate the geographical, and climatic factors that might contribute significantly to the encephalitis endemic in Bihar and their interrelationships with parental behavior. The study would not only be useful for changing parental behavior it would also be helpful for public health professionals for better action plans.

Parental Behavior is usually influenced by living standards, income level, and culture however, it also requires changing or adjusting accordingly to the geographical and climatic conditions. A low-nourished child devoid of adequate parental care could turn extremely vulnerable in an endemic-affected area marred with specific geographical and climatic conditions. Therefore, a shift is needed in parental care most specifically related to nutrition and hygiene including safe water and sanitation.

In addition, the geographical mapping of the endemic-affected areas would provide an opportunity to understand the causes and work on an action plan. The complex challenges posed by public health

threats demanded that public health professionals have a concrete understanding of the relationships among the various factors affecting health. In recent years, public health practitioners have grown increasingly aware of the value Geographic Information Systems (GIS) can add in developing an effective framework for action.

2. Literature Review:

1. **The Role of GIS in Public Health: Geographical Information Systems (GIS)** have become increasingly vital in public health, enabling researchers to map disease patterns, monitor outbreaks, and develop targeted interventions. The use of GIS in public health dates back to the mid-19th century when Dr. John Snow used a hand-drawn map to trace the source of a cholera outbreak in London. This pioneering work demonstrated the potential of spatial analysis in understanding disease diffusion, which continues to be a critical aspect of modern public health efforts (Cromley & McLafferty, 2012).

2. **Environmental and Climatic Influences on Disease Patterns:** Environmental and climatic factors are crucial determinants of disease patterns, particularly in regions like Bihar, where monsoons, floods, and stagnant water create conducive conditions for encephalitis. Studies have shown that these factors significantly contribute to the breeding of mosquitoes, which are primary vectors for the disease. GIS tools can effectively map these environmental conditions, helping public health professionals identify high-risk areas and implement preventive measures (Thomson et al., 2019).

3. **The Intersection of Parental Behavior and Public Health:** Parental behavior, influenced by socio-economic factors, plays a significant role in child health outcomes, especially in endemic regions. In areas prone to encephalitis, inadequate nutrition, poor hygiene, and unsafe water practices increase children's vulnerability. GIS can be used to map these socioeconomic conditions, allowing for more targeted public health interventions that address both environmental and behavioral factors (Sampson, 2020).

4. **GIS in Mapping Disease Diffusion and Informing Public Health Strategies:** The application of GIS in public health extends beyond mapping disease prevalence. It includes analyzing the diffusion patterns of diseases like encephalitis and their association with various environmental and socio-economic factors. This spatial analysis capability is crucial for developing effective public health strategies, such as resource allocation, vaccination campaigns, and community health education programs (Gatrell & Elliott, 2014).

5. **Case Studies in GIS Applications for Encephalitis in Bihar:** Specific case studies, such as those conducted in Muzaffarpur and Gaya districts of Bihar, demonstrate the effectiveness of GIS in identifying disease hotspots and informing public health strategies. These studies highlight the role of environmental conditions, such as proximity to stagnant water bodies and flood-prone areas, in the spread of encephalitis. They also underscore the importance of adapting parental behavior and public health interventions to these local conditions (Kumar et al., 2017).

3. Statement of problem

Encephalitis spreads largely because of environmental and ecological factors. Monsoon is the most susceptible season as it provides enough water for mosquitoes to breed. However, in Bihar cases of encephalitis are also reported during pre-monsoon seasons. The disease is also prevalent in flood-hit areas and areas where there is lots of stagnant water. Floods contaminate groundwater which is one of the causes of encephalitis.

As per estimates, almost 45-50 percent of the Indian population people lives in encephalitis-prone regions of India. The cost of treatment and vaccination could be extremely high. Prevention used to be the best method to save funds. However, encephalitis can affect anyone but elders and infants are more vulnerable. Almost a hundred children die each year in Bihar due to encephalitis and thousands get affected. Outbreak of encephalitis commonly known as “brain fever” occurs particularly during monsoon season. The most common strains are *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome* and *Japanese*

Encephalitis (JE) which hit Bihar every year and cause hundreds of deaths. Usually, encephalitis is the most widespread in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar but it also affects West Bengal and Assam.

Mosquitoes or insect bites, contaminated food and water, and breathing in the respiratory droplets of an infected person can cause Encephalitis. Encephalitis is an acute inflammation of the brain caused by viruses. Its symptoms include fever, headache, drowsiness, confusion, and fatigue. Advance-level symptoms may include convulsions or seizures, tremors, memory problems, and hallucinations. Young children and infants will show symptoms like high fever, poor appetite, and irritability.

Diseases including endemic and epidemic used to grip selected pieces of the population. A certain kind of people as a part of the population always remained at risk due to their ignorance, lack of awareness, inadequate nutrition, hygiene, and medical care. The factors responsible for sickness could well be detected based on minute epidemiological studies. Encephalitis could easily be termed a great endemic in Bihar that usually occurs around *Muzaffarpur* and *Gaya* Districts of Bihar. The two districts are situated at a distance one in the north and the other in the South of river Ganges. The environmental conditions are also not entirely the same despite being largely tropical. The cause of such a massive endemic is believed to involve three HS i.e. *Hunger, Health, and Hygiene*. Therefore, this study would be a humble attempt by the research scholar to investigate the hidden layers of those relationships.

Since ancient times, *Hippocrates* and Indian *Ayurveda* systems believed that diseases occurred due to an imbalance in the body of atoms of air, fire, water, and earth. Therefore, this study would acquire the significance that poor nutrition, hygiene, and environmental conditions are a reason for the *encephalitis* endemic.

4. Objectives:

GIS can be used to solve the problems related to the management of public health programs, as it helps the decision makers to understand their geographical region, know their coverage concerning disease prevalence, and correlate different types of data to understand the probability of concurrence of any epidemics and to overcome with positive solutions to any critical information.

GIS can be a useful tool for observing longitudinal trends, identifying populations at risk, planning and targeting interventions, linking data, forecasting epidemics, monitoring disease patterns and interventions over time, determining geographical distribution and variation of disease (prevalence and incidence) and overall management (eg. Human Resources, Financial, Logistics, and Supply, MIS, etc.) of an effective health care delivery system.

This virtual certificate course will provide participants a platform to introduce fundamental concepts of the use of GIS within the public health context and build practical experience

in the use of open-source GIS software (QGIS) and spatially referenced data for effective program management.

5. Findings:

Epidemiologists employ a range of study designs from observational to experimental and are generally categorized as descriptive, analytic (aiming to further examine known associations or hypothesized relationships), and experimental (a term often equated with clinical or community trials of treatments and other interventions). In observational studies, nature is allowed to “take its course”, as epidemiologists observe from the sidelines. Conversely, in experimental studies, the epidemiologist is the one in control of all of the factors entering a certain case study.

Epidemiological studies are aimed, where possible, at revealing unbiased relationships between exposures such as alcohol or smoking, biological agents, stress, or chemicals to mortality or morbidity. The identification of causal relationships between these exposures and outcomes is an important aspect of epidemiology. Modern epidemiologists use informatics as a tool.

Observational studies have two components: descriptive, and analytical. Descriptive observations pertain to the “who, what, where, and when of health-related state occurrence”. However, analytical observations deal more with the ‘how’ of a health-related event.

Experimental epidemiology contains three case types: randomized control trial (often used for new medicine or drug testing), field trial (conducted on those at a high risk of contracting a disease), and community trial (research on social originating diseases).

Unfortunately, many epidemiology studies conducted cause false or misinterpreted information to circulate to the public. According to a class taught by professor Madhukar Pai MD, PhD at McGill, “...optimism bias is pervasive, most studies biased or inconclusive or false, most discovered true associations are inflated, fear and panic-inducing rather than helpful; media-induced panic, cannot detect small effects; big effects are not to be found anymore”. The term 'epidemiologic triad' is used to describe the intersection of *Host*, *Agent*, and *Environment* in analyzing an outbreak

Geographic information systems (GISs) and Geographic Information Science (GIScience) combine computer-mapping capabilities with additional database management and data analysis tools. Commercial GIS systems are very powerful and have touched many applications and industries, including environmental science, urban planning, agricultural applications, and others.

Public health is another focus area that has made increasing use of GIS techniques. A strict definition of public health is difficult to pin down, as it is used in different ways by different groups. In general, public health differs from personal health in that it is

- (1) focused on the health of populations rather than of individuals,
- (2) focused more on prevention than on treatment, and
- (3) operates in a mainly governmental (rather than private) context.

These efforts fall naturally within the domain of problems requiring the use of spatial analysis as part of the solution, and GIS and other spatial analysis tools are therefore recognized as providing potentially transformational capabilities for public health efforts.

This article presents some history of the use of geographic information and geographic information systems in public health application areas, provides some examples showing the utilization of GIS techniques in solving specific public health problems, and finally addresses several potential issues arising from the increased use of these GIS techniques in the public health arena.

Public health efforts have been based on the analysis and use of spatial data for many years. Dr. John Snow (physician), often credited as the father of epidemiology, is arguably the most famous of those examples.^[2] Dr. Snow used a hand-drawn map to analyze the geographic locations of deaths related to cholera in London in the mid-1850s. His map, which superimposed the locations of cholera deaths with those of public water supplies, pinpointed the Broad Street pump as the most likely source of the cholera outbreak. Removal of the pump handle led to a rapid decline in the incidence of cholera, helping the medical community to eventually conclude that cholera was a water-borne disease.

Dr. Snow's work indicates how a GIS could benefit public health investigations and other research. He continued to analyze his data, eventually showing that the incidence rate of cholera was also related to local elevation as well as soil type and alkalinity. Low-lying areas, particularly those with poorly draining soil, were found to have higher incidence rates for cholera, which Dr. Snow attributed to the pools of water that tended to collect there, again showing evidence that cholera was a water-borne disease (rather than one borne by 'miasma' as was commonly believed at the time).

This is an early example of what has come to be known as disease diffusion mapping, an area of study based on the idea that disease starts from some source or central point and then spreads throughout the local area according to patterns and conditions there. This is another area of research where the capabilities of a GIS are of help to practitioners.

GIS for public health

In the United States of America (USA) GIS technologies are being used to map more modern diseases. The map usually included spread, death toll, and affected households. It helps in controlling the disease.

Today's public health problems are much larger in scope than those Dr. Snow faced, and researchers today depend on modern GIS and other computer mapping applications to assist in their analyses. For example, see the map to the right depicting death rates from heart disease among white males above age 35 in the US between 2000 and 2004.

Public health informatics (PHI) is an emerging specialty that focuses on the application of information science and technology to public health practice and research. As part of that effort, a GIS – or more generally a spatial decision support system (SDSS) – offers improved geographic visualization techniques, leading to faster, better, and more robust understanding and decision-making capabilities in the public health arena.

For example, GIS displays have been used to show a clear relationship between clusters of emergent Hepatitis C cases and those of known intravenous drug users in Connecticut. Causality is difficult to prove – collocation does not establish causation – but confirmation of previously established causal relationships (like intravenous drug use and Hepatitis C) can strengthen acceptance of those relationships, as well as help to demonstrate the utility and reliability of GIS-related solution techniques. Conversely, showing the coincidence of potential causal factors with the ultimate effect can help suggest a potential causal relationship, thereby driving further investigation and analysis (source needed?).

Alternately, GIS techniques have been used to show a lack of correlation between causes and effects or between different effects. For example, the distributions of both birth defects and infant mortality in Iowa were studied, and the researchers found no relationship in those data. This led to the conclusion that birth defects and infant mortality are likely unrelated, and are likely due to different causes and risk factors.

GIS can support public health in different ways as well. First and foremost, GIS displays can help inform proper understanding and drive better decisions. For example, the elimination of health disparities is one of two primary goals of Healthy People 2010, one of the preeminent public health programs in existence today in the US. GIS can play a significant role in that effort, helping public health practitioners identify areas of disparities or inequities, and ideally helping them identify and develop solutions to address those shortcomings. GIS can also help researchers integrate disparate data from a wide variety of sources, and can even be used to enforce quality control measures on those data. Much public health data is still manually generated and is therefore subject to human-generated mistakes and miscoding. For example, geographic analysis of health care data from North Carolina showed that just over 40% of the records contained errors of some sort in the geographic information (city, county, or zip code), errors that would have gone undetected without the visual displays provided by GIS. Correction of these errors led not only to more correct GIS displays but also improved ALL analyses using those data.

There are also concerns or issues with the use of GIS tools for public health efforts. Chief among those is a concern for the privacy and confidentiality of individuals. Public health is concerned about the health of the population as a whole but must use data on the health of individuals to make many of those assessments, and protecting the privacy and confidentiality of those individuals is of paramount importance. The use of GIS displays and related databases raises the potential of compromising those privacy standards, so some precautions are necessary to avoid pinpointing individuals based on spatial data. For example, data may need to be aggregated to cover larger areas such as a zip code or county, helping to mask individual identities. Maps can also be constructed at smaller scales so that less detail is revealed. Alternately, key identifying features (such as the road

and street network) can be left off the maps to mask the exact location, or it may even be advisable to intentionally offset the location markers by some random amount if deemed necessary.

It is well established in the literature that statistical inference based on aggregated data can lead researchers to erroneous conclusions, suggesting relationships that do not exist or obscuring relationships that do exist. This issue is known as the modifiable areal unit problem. For example, New York public health officials worried that cancer clusters and causes would be misidentified after they were forced to post maps showing cancer cases by ZIP code on the internet. They asserted that ZIP codes were designed for a purpose unrelated to public health issues, and so the use of these arbitrary boundaries might lead to inappropriate groupings and then to incorrect conclusions.

6. Conclusion

The use of GIS in public health is an application area still in its infancy. Like most new applications, there is a lot of promise, but also a lot of pitfalls that must be avoided along the way. Many researchers and practitioners are concentrating on this effort, hoping that the benefits outweigh the risks and the costs associated with this emerging application area for modern GIS techniques.

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